

NOTES

Some Mixed-Ligand Chelates of In(III)

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STUDIES on mixed-ligand systems have evoked considerable interest in recent times. Most of these are directed towards elucidation of affinities of secondary ligands for the primary complexes of metals with multidentate ligands of the EDTA type. Such mixed-ligand chelates are obviously formed in cases where the central metal ion is capable of extending its co-ordination to accommodate secondary ligand molecules. Data on a number of systems involving thorium and lanthanide ions have already appeared^{1,2,3}. The Ln(III) ions were found to exhibit a co-ordination number eight⁴. It was therefore of interest to study the behaviour of a trivalent ion like indium. Preliminary experiments indicated that the indium-EDTA complex showed no residual affinity for any secondary ligand indicating that the maximum co-ordination number for indium ion is only six. Solvent extraction studies on mixed-ligand chelates of In(III) with β -diketones at this constant co-ordination have been carried out⁵. Under the circumstances, it was felt that the indium ion, bound to a quadridentate ligand like NTA, would be capable of adding on secondary ligands. The interaction of In(III)-NTA with a number of such ligands was studied potentiometrically and the findings are presented in this communication.

Experimental

Indium solution was prepared by dissolving indium metal (BDH 99.9%) in conc.-HNO₃, evaporating the solution to near dryness and then diluting with 0.1N HNO₃. This solution was standardised by an EDTA titration using xylenol orange as indicator. Nitrilotriacetic acid (E. Merck), Tiron (Fluka), Maltol (K—L Labs) were used as such. Kojic acid (BDH Biochemical grade) and benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) were recrystallised from hot water. The products were checked for their purity by potentiometric titrations.

pH titrations were performed on Radiometer pH meter model pHM 64 equipped with a combination electrode GK 230 IC useful over a pH range 0-12.

A typical set of titration curves is given in Fig. 1. Curves a and b depict the titration of an equimolar

Fig. 1. (a) In(III) 0.0024 M + NTA 0.0024 M
(b) Same as a + Kojic Acid 0.0024 M

mixture of In³⁺ and NTA in the absence and presence of secondary ligand, kojic acid. \bar{n} and pA calculations were performed for the pH interval 3.0 to 5.8 to avoid errors due to the presence of free In³⁺ at low pH values and hydrolysis of In-NTA at higher ones. The formation constants, as calculated from $\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}}$ vs pA plot, are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION

L	In(III)-NTA + L \rightleftharpoons In(III)-NTA-L			
	Tiron	Maltol	Kojic acid	BHA
log K	11.9	7.9	7.1	6.9
log K _H	(i) 12.6*	8.74	7.94	8.98
	(ii) 7.26			

*Literature value

Results and Discussion

All the secondary ligands studied had high pK values. When titrated along with 1 : 1 mixture of In-NTA, the titration curves deviated from parent curves at about pH=3.0 and showed significant inflexions. The extra base consumed corresponded to the titration of protons of the secondary ligand liberated much earlier due to mixed-ligand chelation. The separation between the two curves was used as before¹ for calculation of \bar{n} and pA values.

In-NTA curve gives a sharp inflexion in the pH range 3.0-5.5 followed by a buffer region beyond 5.5 indicating the uptake of hydroxyl ions by the primary In-NTA complex. The inflexion corresponds to the neutralisation of free acid in the In^{3+} solution and the three protons liberated due to combination of NTA with In^{3+} . The concentration of free In^{3+} ions in this pH range can be computed from the formula

$$[M] = \sqrt{\frac{C_M}{K_{\text{prac}}}}$$

where C_M is the total initial metal concentration and K_{prac} is the practical stability constant for the In-NTA complex at the desired pH. At pH=3.0 $K_{\text{prac}} = 10^8$ and hence $[M] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$. At higher pH values, K_{prac} will increase and $[M]$ will decrease further. It can be therefore assumed that in the pH range 3.0 to 5.5, indium exists exclusively as its NTA complex and separation in the titration curves in the presence of secondary ligands can safely be ascribed to the displacement of protons due to the attachment of these ligands to the primary In-NTA complex.

For secondary ligands the order of affinities is Tiron > Maltol > Kojic acid > BHA

All the secondary ligands possess two oxygen donor atoms capable of forming five membered chelate rings. Tiron contains two phenolic groups, maltol and kojic acid one each while BHA contains only an oxime group. The highest affinity of Tiron thus confirms the observation of Martell⁶ that the basic phenolate ion is the most effective co-ordinating group.

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Gravimetric Determination of Bi(III) with Morpholine-4-Carbodithioate

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IN the present investigation, morpholine-4-carbodithioate (MCDT), a new analytical reagent has been employed for the gravimetric determination of Bi(III) in presence of several metal ions. The

reagent (MCDT) precipitates Bi(III) from bismuth nitrate solution quantitatively in the pH range 3.5 to 6.5. The complex formed, was yellow granular of composition $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_3$. The precipitate was dried at 110-120° and weighed. The chelate is thermally stable up to 200°.

Though Bayer and Ott¹ had reported morpholine-4-carbodithioate as possible analytical reagent but no systematic study has been made previously for the determination of Bi(III). In the present study an attempt has been made for the determination of Bi(III) gravimetrically in the presence of commonly occurring metal ions by means of morpholine-4-carbodithioate. The thermogravimetric analysis was also carried out with the view to know the nature of decomposition.

Experimental

Reagent: The potassium salt of the reagent was prepared by mixing potassium hydroxide, morpholine and carbon disulphide in ether at 0° in a ratio 1 : 1 : 1. The purity of the reagent was confirmed by elemental analysis and I.R. spectra. All the chemicals used were of G.R. or Analar grades of E. Merk and B.D.H. The aqueous stock solutions of reagent and bismuth nitrate were prepared in double distilled water.

Determination of Bi(III)

In a 500 ml beaker, 10 ml of 0.20M solution of bismuth nitrate and about 150 ml of distilled water were heated at 50° on a water bath. Then three fold excess of 1%(w/v) aqueous solution of the reagent was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by acetate buffer to adjust the pH in the range 3.5 to 5.5. The contents of the beaker were digested for about 30 minutes over water bath, filtered through a sintered crucible (G_4) and washed thoroughly with water. The complex was dried at 110-120° and weighed as $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_3$. The conversion factor (Bismuth/Bismuth complex) was 0.3004.

The thermolysis curve of bismuth complex had horizontal portion extending up to 180°. Above 180° it decomposes slowly upto 250°; thereafter it decomposes rapidly up to 325°. Above this temperature, again a slow decomposition occurs, and at 560°, the weight of the residue becomes constant.

Determination of Bi(III) in Presence of Foreign Ions:

A 10 ml of 0.02 M of Bi(III) solution was mixed with a known amount of foreign ion and diluted to 150 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0 by using acetate buffer. A mixture of an ammoniacal EDTA and sodium potassium tartrate solution was added to mask the Tl(I), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), In(III) and Ga(III) metal ions. In case of oxo-vanadium(IV) and oxo-titanium(IV), 1 g of sodium fluoride was added and the contents